

Personal Laws and Legal Pluralism: An Obstacle to Uniform Gender Rights

Paper Id : 20528 Submission Date : 2025-07-27 Acceptance Date : 2025-08-11 Publication Date : 2025-08-13

This is an open-access research paper/article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.16871973

For verification of this paper, please visit on <http://www.socialresearchfoundation.com/anthology.php#8>

Chhavi Ahlawat

Assistant Professor
Department Of Law
Amity University
Noida, Uttar Pradesh, India

Abstract

India is a diversified nation and is a home to in numerous communities, religions, castes, race, sects and so on. These varieties of communities have been living together in the society since ancient times and subsequently started adopting and framing new cultures, traditions and so on. One of the key features of India is secularism and the secular nature of India should be only confined with the matters of religion. The freedom of Religion is a personal matter. However, with time, it got connected with the legal rights as well. This amalgamation gave rise to the variety of personal laws which deals with the provisions of marriage, inheritance, adoption, divorce, guardianship and so on, which are connected to the family issues. This has resulted in the non-compliance with the fundamental provisions of the Constitution of India, particularly its cardinal principles- justice, equality, liberty and fraternity. Constitution is the supreme law of India. However, the clash between personal and religious laws has been a major factor in the growing number of court cases involving violations of people's rights, especially those of women, as well as the patriarchal system that has been ingrained in Indian society, which has led to biased customs. As the protector of the Indian Constitution, the judiciary has been actively highlighting problems with these personal laws and how they undermine the goal of the Constitution, which is to preserve "unity in diversity."

Keywords

Secularism, Personal Laws, Freedom of Religion, Judiciary, Unity in Diversity.

Introduction

The Indian society is an amalgamation of the variety of communities, religions, traditions, cultures, races etc. timing back to the Indus Valley Civilization and beyond. One of the remarkable aspects of the Indian society is its ability to accommodate people from the diverse religious and cultural backgrounds, who have coexisted in relative harmony despite following their distinct customs and traditions. Secularism is one of the fundamental characteristics of the Indian state, which recognizes no official religion. By ensuring that the State does not favor or discriminate against any particular faith, the Constitution of India upholds a neutral stance towards all the religions in India. Part III of the Constitution of India, which deals with the Fundamental Rights also deals with the principle of equal treatment. Specifically, the Freedom of Religion[1] allows every individual of India to freely practice, profess and propagate any religion of their choice. However, these Fundamental Rights are not absolute in nature and can be restricted for reasonable purposes, in the interest of morality, health, public order and other constitutional considerations. All the three organs of the Government- Executive, Legislature and Judiciary play a major role in safeguarding these rights. Among them, the Judiciary acts as a primary watchdog of the Constitution of India and makes sure that there exist no such laws which violate or infringe the Fundamental Rights of any individual and provides constitutional remedies[2] to the people, enabling them to seek redressal when their rights get violated.

Customs have played a major role in shaping the personal laws of each religious community. Under personal laws, customs are honoured but not infallible. Only when they fulfil legal requirements and don't go against public policy or statute law do they enjoy immunity. Particularly when it comes to gender discrimination or child safety, courts are essential in weeding out exploitative or regressive practices. Some customs have been given immunity in these personal laws as what traditions and values have been deeply rooted in the Indian diversified society, it is not an easy task to remove them. One of the examples is that under the personal law of Hindu religion, with respect to the ceremonial customs, if one community is following Saptapadi (seven steps before the marriage), then it is valid, whereas if any other community is following Gandharva (mutual consent without the rituals) instead of Saptapadi, then also it may be considered as valid if they are allowed in customs. Another example is, that in the personal laws of Muslims, before being outlawed by the Act of 2019,[3] triple talaq was accepted as a customary form of divorce.

The 42nd Amendment Act of 1976 formally incorporated the term 'secular' into the Preamble, reaffirming the nation's commitment to religious neutrality and equal respect for all faiths. Secularism is one of the fundamental features of the Constitution of India. In India, the concept of 'positive secularism' is followed. The State, although, keeps a moral distance from all religions but does not act indifferently toward them, according to positive

secularism. It guarantees that all religions receive the same respect and acknowledgement and steps in when needed to defend constitutional principles such as justice, equality, and human dignity.

Although the Constitution of India protects the religious freedom,[4] it also gives the government the authority to intervene due to reasonable purposes such as health, morality, public order and other constitutional reasons. Although the state does not have an official religion, it does promote religious minorities, provide funding for religious organizations, and step in when discriminatory or exploitative religious activities occur. It has, for instance, changed the religious customs in the past such as, abolishing untouchability, made certain amendments in the personal laws that were discriminatory, and so on. With time, numerous customary practices developed into personal laws specific to different religious communities. However, this legal pluralism has many a times come into conflict with the constitutional principles of equality, especially because it allows for the divergent practices on the civil issues regarding marriage, inheritance, succession, guardianship and adoption. Such differences have resulted in the unequal treatment, particularly in the context of gender justice and the uniform civil rights.

Religious rights differ from the family rights and for being the two different areas, they must not be confused and considered to be in the same category. With respect to the freedom of religion, it protects the individual's own beliefs, faith and practices, which fall under the category of religious rights. While on the other hand, the family rights pertain to those civil issues which are frequently covered by the civil laws and have wider social ramifications, such as inheritance, divorce, marriage, adoption and so on. The junction of the family rights and religious rights, which gave rise to the personal laws, has resulted in the generation of various constitutional and legal challenges that have drawn attention of the Judiciary in the recent years. Judiciary, being the guardian of the Constitution of India has been playing an active role to identify these issues and to eliminate such provisions from the personal laws which are derogatory and infringe the Fundamental Rights of the individuals of the nation, particularly of women.

Objective of study

1. To determine and evaluate the type and extent of the personal laws in India for different religious groups (Christians, Muslims, Hindus etc.).
2. To draw attention to the situations in which gender-based discrimination has resulted from the personal laws, particularly in relation to guardianship, divorce, inheritance, and marriage.
3. To look at the rulings and interpretations of the Court that, in light of the constitutional rights, either support or contradict the personal laws.
4. To look into how much the denial of the gender rights is a result of the legal pluralism.
5. To make recommendations for legislative and policy changes that will bring personal laws into compliance with the Fundamental Rights protected by the Constitution of India.

Review of Literature

There has been much discussion in scholarly, judicial, and policy-making circles over legal plurality and personal laws in India. Although legal diversity enables communities to maintain their distinct religious and cultural identities, scholars and jurists have long maintained that this often comes at the expense of gender fairness and constitutional uniformity.

The Constitution and Equality of Gender

The Fundamental Rights that prioritize equality, non-discrimination and individual liberty are guaranteed under the Constitution of India. For instance, Article 14 (Equal protection under the law and equality before the law), Article 15 (Discrimination on the basis of religion, race, caste, sex, or place of birth is forbidden), Article 21 (right to life and personal liberty)

However, because religion personal laws are protected, their execution is still socially and politically problematic.

Personal laws and disparities in gender

India has a wide variety of personal laws since they are derived from the religious texts and customs. As an illustration, The Hindu Succession Act of 1956 granted daughters minimal property rights prior to 2005 amendment. The Muslim personal law raises questions regarding gender equality by allowing polygamy and unilateral divorce (talaq). Before amendments, women had to prove their divorces more strongly than men under the Christian personal laws.

The role of Judiciary in interpretation of the provisions of the personal laws

The Indian Judiciary has been playing a proactive role to question and reform the personal laws that violate the Constitutional Rights of the people of the country. The cases such as Shayara Bano, Gita Hariharan, Vineeta Sharma etc., reflect on the ongoing judicial attempt to debate religious freedom with gender equality, often prioritizing constitutional morality over the customary practices.

Main Text

Legal Pluralism: Meaning and Its Existence in the Indian Society

India is a nation characterized by immense diversity in culture, language, customs and traditions across its different regions. Such pluralistic identity of India also extends to the legal sphere as well. The Seventh Schedule of the Constitution of India, which divides

the powers between the Union and the States in the form of three Lists- Union List, State List and the Concurrent List, there are also mentioned several legislative subjects in them accordingly. Notably, the Concurrent List (List III) includes the matters related to family and personal laws. It enables both the Union as well as the State Governments to legislate on such matters.

Under this framework, the term 'legal pluralism' emerges as one of the defining features of the legal system in India. It refers to the coexistence of the multiple legal systems within a single jurisdiction which is a result of the geographical diversity of the country as well as the existence of numerous cultural and religious communities. The main objective of 'legal pluralism' is to address the distinctive needs and practices of variety of social groups in such a manner that is locally relevant as well as context-sensitive at the same time.[5]

However, the outcome of the application of legal pluralism in the realm of the personal laws has been the rise of deep social and legal fragmentation. In India, each religious community is being governed by its own set of the personal laws which deal with the matters relating to marriage, succession, divorce. Adoption, inheritance and guardianship. For instance, there are distinct personal laws governing the religious communities like Hindus, Muslims, Christians as well as Parsis. Some of their personal laws are codified while others are based on the religious scriptures as well as the customary practices. Consequently, the individuals, solely based on their religion, are subject to the different legal standards. This results into the creation of complex and often unequal legal landscape. On one hand, such a pluralistic arrangement may appear to guard the cultural autonomy of the country, but on the other hand, it has also lead to the significant disparities in the protection of the individual's rights, especially the gender rights, across different religious communities. This legal pluralism, though constitutionally recognized, has also become a barrier to the attainment of uniform gender justice.

The idea of justice as enshrined in the Constitution of India is to ensure fairness to all the individuals of the country in the spheres of economy, society as well as politics. It ensures that the constitutional commitment towards attaining equality[6] and non-discrimination,[7] is affirmed. This protection also recognizes the concept of 'positive discrimination' (or affirmed action) in order to uplift the historically disadvantaged section of the society[8]. However, the existence of legal pluralism, especially in the realm of the personal laws, has resulted into the systemic gender inequality. There are certain provisions within the personal laws, which are largely derived from the customary practices, that continue to reflect the patriarchal mindset of the society that disproportionately affect the rights of the women. These customary practices, which are now embedded within the provisions of the personal laws, were shaped during the times when patriarchal system was immensely entrenched in the Indian society. While, so many discriminatory and derogatory practices such as sati, Jauhar, triple talaq, female foeticide, child marriage and so on, have been either abolished or criminalized over time, many practices that are gender-biased, still persist, especially within the framework of the personal laws. This negatively affects the enjoyment of the civil rights of the people. One of the striking examples is the practice of polygamy, which is permitted under the Muslim personal law but is prohibited under the Hindu personal law.

These types of inconsistencies highlight the tensions between the legal pluralism and the vision of Constitution of India towards achieving its goals of gender justice upto full extent. They also raise serious questions about whether or not the freedom of religion should override the right to equality, guaranteed under the Constitution [14] of India.

Personal Laws v. Gender Equality

One of the major issues with the provisions of the personal laws is their inconsistencies with the principles of the Constitution of India. These personal laws that are applicable across the country have widely been shaped by the patriarchal mindset of the society which was at its peak during the Rig Vedic era and it continues to exist even today in some or the other way. The patriarchal values have lead the degradation of the women by limiting or supressing their rights, socially, economically and politically. These values have been embedded in the roots of the Indian society so well that it is really difficult to separate them from the people. While the Constitution of India came into force on January 26, 1950, it sought to address all the existing deficiencies within the Indian society by making sure that no individual would be subjected to any form of discrimination and that every citizen would enjoy equal rights and opportunities.

However, the conflict between the discriminatory provisions of the personal laws and the egalitarian principles of the Constitution of India, has been one of the significant factors, hindering the true unity among the various religious communities within the Indian society. This highlights the importance of one of the provisions of the Constitution of India under Part III[9]. It states that any legislation that were in effect before to the Constitution's adoption and that conflict with Part III's (the Fundamental Rights) provisions, are null and void[10]. The State is also not allowed to enact laws that restrict or eliminate fundamental rights[11]. This implies, in principle, that any sex-based discriminatory provision in personal laws ought to be declared illegal. In actuality, though, the situation is more complicated.

The Supreme Court, in one of the cases, ruled that, the personal laws are not "laws" in the sense of Article 13 and, as a result, cannot be directly challenged for breaching the Fundamental Rights. The Court reasoned that personal laws are not covered by Article 13 since they are not passed by the legislature but rather are based on religious texts and traditions. Wide-ranging effects resulted from this interpretation, which essentially shielded numerous gender-discriminatory clauses in private legislation from close examination under the Constitution of India. Because of this, changes to personal legislation have frequently required indirect judicial interpretation or legislative revision rather than the direct application of the Article.

One of the key principles as enshrined under the Constitution of India is the provision of Justice (social, economical and political)[13]. One of the essential components of the social justice is 'gender justice' which finds its protection within the ambit of Part III of the Constitution of India which guarantees Fundamental Rights to all the citizens of the country. The Constitution of India, being the supreme law of the country, leaves no room for any legislation, whether statutory or otherwise, that undermines the dignity and equality of the individuals of the nation. While the criminal laws and most civil laws in India are secular in nature and are free from any explicit discriminatory provisions, the personal laws, although forming part of the civil law sphere, remain riddled with the norms that perpetuate gender equality in the society. These laws, derived from the religious traditions and customs, contain the provisions relating to marriage, guardianship, succession, adoption, inheritance, and so on, that often they operate to the disadvantage of women.

Such unequal and distinct provisions contained in the personal laws not only hinder the individuals from fully enjoying their civil rights but they also create divisions within the society by undermining the unity envisaged by the framers of the Constitution of India. The continued existence of the gender-biased or gender-discriminatory personal law provisions erodes the foundational ideals of justice, fraternity and equality on which the Constitution of India stands. It is therefore imperative that reforms are initiated proactively and without waiting for any judicial intervention in the form of litigation, so that such discriminatory provisions can be reviewed and abolished through action in alignment with the constitutional principles.

Judiciary: Caretaker of the Constitutional Principles

The Indian judiciary, which serves as the ultimate protector and interpreter of the supreme law of the land, is essential to maintaining the values outlined in the Constitution of India. The Constitution's authors envisioned an independent judiciary that would operate as a check on any executive or legislative activities that went against the constitution's directives. In a multicultural and heterogeneous nation like India, where conflicts frequently emerge between religiously based personal rules and the constitutional guarantees of equality and justice, this is especially important.

When political sensitivities or legislative lethargy have delayed to make reforms to the personal laws, the Indian judiciary has been instrumental in defending individual rights and enforcing constitutional norms. Religious conventions and traditions are frequently the source of personal laws, which regulate issues like marriage, divorce, inheritance, adoption, and succession. Although these laws are meant to honour the cultural autonomy of different communities, they occasionally include gender-based discriminatory clauses that violate the equality guaranteed by the Constitution. In order to defend individual rights and lessen the discriminatory effects of personal laws, the judiciary has creatively construed constitutional provisions, frequently choosing the morality of the constitution over social or religious morality.

There are some instances where the Indian Judiciary defended the rights of the individuals from the discriminatory provisions of the personal laws. Few of its judgments are mentioned hereinunder.

1. In one of the cases, the Supreme Court of India abolished the practice of talaq-e-biddat (triple talaq), declaring it as unconstitutional as it violated the equality and dignity of Muslim women[15]. This decision of the Supreme Court marked a watershed moment in asserting that the religious practices, even if claimed as part of the personal laws, can never override the Fundamental Rights.
2. In another case[16] the Court struck down the provisions of the Act of 1917 [17] which denied the equal inheritance rights to the Syrian Christian women, making sure that they were entitled to the same share as men under the Act of 1925 [18].
3. The Supreme Court in another case interpreted the term "after" under one of the provisions of the Act of 1956,[19] to mean "in the absence of" hence recognizing the mothers, alongside fathers, as the natural guardians of their minor children, strengthening gender equality in the guardianship rights [20].
4. In another landmark ruling, the Supreme Court affirmed that the daughters born after the amendment in 2005 to the Act of 1956, [21] still hold the equal coparcenary rights in the ancestral property, regardless of whether their father was alive at the time of the amendment or not. This judgment reinforced the gender-neutral property rights under the Hindu law [22].
5. The Supreme Court had struck down one of the provisions of the IPC [23] (dealing with adultery law) as it deemed it unconstitutional because it treated women as

property of the husband. This decision upheld the autonomy and dignity of women [24].

In the fight to overturn discriminatory elements in personal laws, the Indian Judiciary has become a formidable force. Legislative inaction has resulted in substantial gaps that the Courts have filled through progressive interpretations and reliance on constitutional morality. A truly egalitarian legal system, however, requires ongoing cooperation between the legislature and the Court to guarantee that individual laws are consistent with the equality, justice, and dignity contained in the Constitution of India. Nonetheless, notwithstanding these actions, the judiciary cannot completely amend personal laws without going too far into the legislative branch. It cannot proactively stop a discriminatory practice unless a case is brought before it because its work is largely interpretive and remedial. To remove gender discrimination in personal laws, this restriction emphasizes the necessity of both judicial activism and legislative reform

Conclusion

The fundamental tenets of the Constitution of India are social, economic, and political justice, equality, and non-discrimination. Personal laws continue to be divided along the religious lines because of the existence of legal pluralism, whereas criminal and other secular civil laws are uniformly applicable. These laws frequently include clauses that uphold gender inequality, especially against women, and are based on religious doctrine and historical norms. Discriminatory personal law provisions persist notwithstanding constitutional guarantees found in Part III of the Constitution of India [25] as well as the mandate found in it that declares laws incompatible with Fundamental Rights unconstitutional [26]. The judicial interventions have assisted in the removal of some gender-unjust clauses. Piecemeal reform, however, is inadequate. A comprehensive strategy is necessary to establish true gender fairness and balance personal laws with constitutional morals.

In India, issues like marriage, divorce, inheritance, and adoption have traditionally been controlled by personal laws that have their roots in religion and custom. Gender-based discrimination has occurred from legal pluralism's coexistence with the constitutional requirement of equality, despite its goal of respecting cultural diversity. Women in all communities frequently have restricted guardianship authority, limited marital autonomy, and unequal property rights. A conflict between the principles of cultural preservation and the basic right to equality guaranteed by the Constitution is evident in the continuance of such disparities. Personal laws must be changed to conform to constitutional morality rather than religious dogma if true gender fairness is to be realized. Systematic discrimination must be eliminated and gender justice must be guaranteed across cultural divides. In order to create a society where constitutional ideals prevail over discriminatory customs, the selective application of equality in personal legislation must be replaced with a rights-based, inclusive approach

Suggestions for the future Study

1. Personal law codification and uniformity
2. Remove discriminatory clauses and maintain culturally neutral practices by combining all the personal laws under a single legal framework.
3. Amendments that consider Gender equality
4. Ensure that men and women have equal rights and responsibilities under all the laws pertaining to marriage, adoption, succession, divorce and maintenance.
5. Morality as a guideline in the Constitution
6. When deciding the conflicts of the personal law, apply constitutional morality as the standard rather than the religious morality.
7. Examining discriminatory practices in the Court
8. Require judicial review of the personal laws on a regular basis in order to find and invalidate any provisions that infringe upon the Fundamental Rights.
9. Consultation with the Stakeholders and Inclusive Discussion
10. Involve community representatives, legal experts, women's rights organizations, and religious leaders in the creation of reforms to guarantee the acceptance and prevent hostility.
11. Organize campaigns for Legal Literacy and Public Awareness
12. Start National initiatives to inform people about their legal rights and potential remedies, with a focus on women.
13. Implementing a Uniform Civil Code (UCC) gradually
14. Start with universally acceptable elements of the UCC such as guardianship, inheritance, maintenance etc. and introduce it gradually.
15. Enhanced enforcement systems
16. Create expedited family courts and sever sanctions for infractions to guarantee the successful application of the amended personal laws.

References

1. *The Constitution of India, arts. 25, 26.*
2. *The Constitution of India, arts. 32, 226.*
3. *Muslim Women (Protection of Rights on Marriage) Act, 2019*
4. *The Constitution of India, arts 25, 26, 27, 28.*
5. *SPECIAL EDITORIAL NOTE ON UNIFORM CIVIL CODE, LEGAL PLURALISM AND THE CONSTITUTION OF INDIA (last visited on August 01, 2025).*
6. *The Constitution of India, art. 14.*
7. *The Constitution of India, art. 15.*

8. *Shafaque Ammar, "Concept of Justice in the Indian Constitution" 15 International Journal of Research in Social Sciences*53 (2025).
9. *The Constitution of India, art. 13.*
10. *The Constitution of India, art. 13(1).*
11. *The Constitution of India, art. 13(2).*
12. *State of Bombay v. Narasu Appa Mali, AIR 1952.*
13. *Provisions of the Constitution of India which are specially relevant to the Ministry of Social Justice & Empowerment*
14. *The Constitution of India, arts. 14,15,21.*
15. *Shayara Bano v. Union of India(2017) 9 SCC.*
16. *Mary Roy v. State of Kerala (1986) 2 SCC 209.*
17. *The Travancore Christian Succession Act, 1917 (Act 2 of 1917).*
18. *The Indian Succession Act, 1925 (Act 39 of 1925).*
19. *The Hindu Minority and Guardianship Act, 1956(Act 32 of 1956).*
20. *Githa Hariharan &Anr. v. Reserve Bank of India &Anr. (1999) 2 SCC 228.*
21. *Hindu Succession (Amendment) Act, 2005 (Act 39 of 2005).*
22. *Vineeta Sharma v. Rakesh Sharma & Ors.(2020) 9 SCC 1.*
23. *The Indian Penal Code, 1860 (Act 45 of 1860).*
24. *Joseph Shine v. Union of India (2019) 3 SCC 39.*
25. *The Constitution of India, arts. 14, 15, 21.*
26. *The Constitution of India, art. 13.*